

Using ML to close the vocabulary gap in the context of environment and climate change in Chichewa

Amelia Taylor, University of Malawi, The Polytechnic, ataylor@poly.ac.mw

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Chichewa, with its geographical dialects¹, is the language of about half of Malawians, spoken both in rural and urban places. Other notable languages are Chiyao and Tumbuka each spoken by about 10% of the population, Chilomwe and Chisena spoken each by about 2% of the population. From 1907 to 1964, Malawi was a British protectorate and the schooling education in the country was in the hands of the Christian missionaries with small governmental input. Missionaries taught English, but at the same time they engaged in learning the local language, conducting significant linguistic work (e.g., writing the first dictionaries and grammatical rules) and engaging in the translation of the Bible in the main local languages of Chichewa, Yao and Tumbuka. Over the years and more significantly, after Malawi became a Republic in 1964, the government assumed a more active role in education by opening schools, and offering universal primary education. Malawi's primary school education shifted towards using Chichewa as the language of instruction. Chichewa as designated a national language alongside English, the latter was used for official and business matters. In secondary schools and higher education, English is used in teaching and learning. The language policy in Malawi education has been an issue of debate, with some arguing that the use of the native vernacular will improve children's learning of new concepts, while others arguing that the need for 'language switching' (mainly between English and Chichewa) in classrooms brings tensions and pressures especially in the teaching of abstract and science subjects (Kapesi, 2011), while others brought special attention to a worrying 'vocabulary gap' that exists between Chichewa and other official indigenous

languages of Malawi (Chiuye, Moyo 2008). The lack of adequate teaching and learning materials in local languages creates 'linguistically impoverished and deprived' learners (Kamwendo, 2016) and there is a need to '*develop terminologies and a broad lexical base*'. This will help in '*diffusing and refuting stereotype notions that indigenous African languages lack a conceptual framework to express scientific notions with appropriate scientific vocabulary*' (Chiuye, Moyo 2008). Studies on the impact of language switching on the teaching of mathematics in schools in Malawi, showed that, although teachers had problems in translating and finding the terminology that best describes some of the mathematical concepts, they did not receive systematic training in the use of language (Kapesi, 2011). Vernaculars and glossary of terms will help children understand concepts that they would otherwise find difficult to understand if taught only in English (Kayambazithu, 1998).

Malawi is a beautiful country with a varied ecosystem (most known being Lake Malawi), grasslands areas and forests. These ecosystems have seen massive degradation over the years. Efforts to restore the habitat, wild animals and protect the forests have been made by international organisations working with the Malawi government (UNESCO, 2017). It is not the purpose of this proposal to discuss all of these, but to emphasise that all these players recognise the need to increase knowledge and awareness about climate change that is available to school children and their educators. Large amounts of money have been spent by international supported campaigns through posters, community

¹ Chewa, Nyanja and Mang'anja.

discussions and recently, videos², to encourage the planting of trees, public and personal sanitation, and avoid littering and charcoal burning. A recent comprehensive study on the charcoal market in Malawi, noted that there is a scarcity of accurate and good quality information on the state of things in Malawi, and that contributes to the maintaining of the status quo and a continuing degradation of the environment (Kambewa, Mataya et al, 2007) .

There seems to be a paradox between the fact that Africans are now seen to be environmentally unfriendly and cannot be expected to make substantive contributions to the world's environmental problem (Ikuenobe 2014), and the African conception of the world, *ubuntu*³, in which man is seen to exist in harmony with nature and thus articulates a moral attitude towards the environment. While these are complex issues, it is evident that communication in the local languages about these issues plays an essential role. In a study on the causes of deforestation in Mwazisi (near Vwaza Marsh Game Reserve), low level of awareness among those in the local population regarding forest use and management was identified as one of the factors contributing to forestry cover reduction (Ngwira, Susan and Watanabe, 2019). 'Traditional ecological knowledge, that is, local people's classification, knowledge, and use of the natural world, their ecological concepts, and their resource management institutions and practices' is at an especially high risk of disappearing if not adequately documented (Maffi 2001).

In the west, alienation from nature and a growing incapacity to experience it, have led educators to incorporate long term educational programs in schools, to bring pupils in contact with nature and to enhance

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<http://www.malawi-music.com/T/2498-tanaka/6037-chilengedwe/11085-chilengedwe-ft-vic-hamjee-tawina-prod-khoh-gomzy>

³ Ubuntu is a Nguni Bantu term meaning "humanity."

their understanding of issues related to the environment and its protection. Special focus is given to pupils using 'talk' to organise, and express their ideas, opinions and feelings about their environment imaginatively (The UK National Association for Environmental Education)⁴. There is a clear emphasis on learning, on using scientific language and the correct use of vocabulary in context but also to explain meaning. Alienation from nature is happening in Africa too, although in different ways. For example, some have pointed out that a large portion of the indigenous vocabulary and knowledge remains unknown or is slowly disappearing (Ikuenobe 2014), (Cloete, 2011). From a list of more than 20 categorisations of landscape types in the language Xitsonga, compiled by Wolmer very few are now recognised by the younger generation (Wolmer, 2007). The list demonstrates centuries of keen observation and experience of the local population, with terms ranging from words such as *Kuthuma* denoting thicket (hiding places of hyenas, leopards and lions) to *Patsa* denoting open areas where buffaloes graze, to *Chawunga /mananga*, denoting a remote, quiet and fearful area where only birds, and wild animals are found. Each of these terms encapsulates a rich meaning about what it defines. Many of these terms are now lost to urbanized Xitsonga speakers (Cloete, 2011).

There is a need therefore to bridge the vocabulary gap by creating glossaries that allow learners to name the environment around them and thus recognise issues of climate change by 'maintain as much control over meanings as possible' because 'by naming the world people name their realities. (Smith, L.T., 1999).

⁴ Similarly, the Government of Malawi published a 'Climate Change Sourcebook for Primary School Teachers' in support of its National Climate Change Learning Strategy, developed under the UN CC:Learn Partnership. 'The sourcebook promotes the integration of climate change education into schools with the goal of shifting an entire young generation of Malawians toward climate-friendly practices.'

The role of ML

We believe that ML has a role to play in closing the ‘vocabulary gap’ of terms and concepts regarding the environment and climate change that exists in Chichewa and other Malawian languages by helping to create a visual dictionary of key terms used to describe the environment and explain the issues involved in climate change and their meaning. Chichewa is a descriptive language, one English term may be translated using several words. For example, “pollution”, without specifying what kind of pollution it refers to, does not have a direct counterpart in Chichewa. “Air pollution” may be translated as “kuwonongeka kwa mpwenya wa chilengedwe”, where ‘chilengedwe’ may mean environment but usually is used to mean ‘creation’, and is also used to refer to “natural resources”, “luso lachilengedwe’.

There are several practical steps in which ML can be used. We propose the task of building of a glossary for the environmental science (similar to the one on wikipedia for English⁵), in Chichewa and other local languages used in Malawi using text available on the internet. Some of this text is obtained by machine-generated translations but some is written by native speakers. The interesting thing is not to detect just literal translations (where these are possible), but also translations by means of ‘descriptions’ and illustrations and thus extract correspondence between terms used and perhaps a measure of how appropriate a term is to convey the meaning intended. As part of this project, ML can be used to identify ‘loanword patterns’, which may be useful in understanding the transmission of cultural items. In many Bantu languages (such as Chichewa), lexical borrowings may be distinguished from the inherited vocabulary on the basis of phonological irregularities.

The vocabulary thus created using ML, can be curated by a Chichewa linguist/ speaker. The

following examples of translations were done by Paul Kazembe, a senior teacher who teaches Chichewa as a Secondary school subject. Paul’s translation can also inform the algorithms used to extract various definitions. We are using in this proposal some of his translations. I have asked that he translated a list of terms first using no technical books or dictionaries, purely by using his own understanding (Appendix A).

Words such as ‘arable land’ have an established meaning in Chichewa ‘malo olima’ - which literally means ‘the land of the farmer’ or ‘agricultural land’ . There is also possibly a borrowed term that is used and Paul translated ‘arable land’ as ‘minda’.

Terms such as ‘acid rain’ are hard to translate. The Chichewa for rain is ‘mvula’. Hence a translation by description is used. Notice that the word ‘acid’ is a loan word from English.

Mvula kapenanso madzi ogwa kuchokera mlengalenga omwe amakhala ndi asidi.

Similarly in translating ‘manure’ the loan word ‘manyowa’ may be used or the expression ‘zinyalala zowolerana’.

Another good example is the word ‘aquaculture’ which was translated by Paul as ‘Ulimi wa za mmadzi’ which literally means ‘farming on water’ and will need a contextual description in order to be fully understood.

The term “adaptation (to environment)” was translated as “kuyanjana ndi nyango” which literally means “reconciliation with the climate” (the word kuyanjana means reconciliation) or ‘Kugwirizana ndi malo’ where ‘malo’ literally means place and kugwirizana means agreement, relationship or union.

The same for ‘carbon footprint’, which Paul translated loosely as ‘kuyeza’, but a definition by description is more appropriate:

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https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Glossary_of_environmental_science

Kuchulukwa kwa mpweya woipa omwe watumizidwa mlengalenga nawononga chilengedwe kwa nthawi yonse yomwe: Machiniwo akhala akugwiritsidwa ntchito. Kapena chipangireni chinthu china chake.

Words such as backflow, carbon neutral, cell, condensation, consumer, drainage, fossil fuel, groundwater, habitat, landfill are hard to translate in Chichewa and need a translation by context or illustration, hence are harder to translate immediately even by language proficient like Paul who has a rich English and Chichewa vocabulary.

What is propose is as follows:

(1) To gather content from the internet in Chichewa on the topics of environment, descriptions of nature and wildlife, climate change. Some text will be original writings in Chichewa, some would be human translation of articles written in English or other languages (or based on these articles), and some will be context generated using machine translators (for example based on Google translate). ML techniques can be used to aid in detecting the type of document and de-coding the translation to identify key terms (Bahdanau, 2014) (Baroni and Bernardini ,2006) although this requires the construction of a large parallel corpus.

(2) To create and use a seed list of translation approximations or descriptions from language teachers such as Paul, and dictionary definitions from Chichewa-English dictionaries.

(3) To use ML (e.g., Word2Vec training strategies) to generate a glossary of environmental terms together with meaning, examples of usage, and a measure of how appropriate a term is to convey the meaning intended e.g., based on ‘selective concept extractions’ (Riloff, 1993).

(4) To use ML to analyse similarities between Chichewa texts and English text on climate change to detect loan words and the presence

of code-switching (Ehara and Kumiko, 2008, Yilmaz et al, 2016).

(5) To tag images which appear inline text by using both the content surrounding them and actual picture captions and this to add a pictorial representation of the terms of the glossary (Devlin, Jacob, et al., 2015, Bai and Shan 2018).

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Appendix . Chichewa translations for climate change related terms (Paul Kazembe). When a translation is not known, there are empty columns.

<u>Term/concept English</u>	<u>Term(s)/concept(s) in Chichewa</u>	<u>Chichewa Approx. Translation when a satisfactory term does not exist in the language</u>
Acid Rain	Mvula Mvula ya asidi.	Mvula kapenanso madzi ogwa kuchokera mlengalenga omwe amakhala ndi asidi.
Adaptation	Kuyanjana ndi nyengo Kugwirizana ndi malo	Kuyanjana ndi nyengo komanso malo nakhazikika pamalo pamene chinthu chili/ munthu ali.
Afforestation	Kudzala mitengo.	Kupanga nkhalango podzala mitengo malo amene analibe mitengoyo.
Agroforestry	Ulimi wamasomphe nya	Kuchita ulimi ukumateteza ndinso kumasamala zachilengedwe pomadzala mitengo ncholinga choteteza mitengo mu ulimi wa phindu.
Air pollution	Kuwonongeka kwa mpweya	Kuwonongeka kwa mpweya
Alternative Fuel	Njira zina zamakono	Zinthu zina zomwe zimagwiritsidwa ntchito ndi anthu zomwe sizimatulutsa utsi wambiri wowononga chilengedwe. Izo zimatulutsa utsi ochepa wowononga zachilengedwe kusiyana ndi zomwe zakhala zikugwiritsidwa ntchito.
Anoxic	Mpweya wochepa	Kukhala ndi mpweya wopumirawu

		wochepetsetsa.
Anthropogenic	Luso Nzeru za umunthu	Chinthu chopangidwa kuchokera ku nzeru za umunthu
Aquaculture	Ulimi wa nsomba. Ulimi wa za mmadzi.	Ulimi womasunga nyama namalima zomera za mmadzi pogwiritsa ntchito njira zamakono.
Aquifer	Make madzi Chithanthwe	Dwale la pansi panthaka lomwe limalandira, kusungana ndinso kupereka madzi ku zitsime komanso ku a kasupe.
Arable Land	Minda Madimba	Malo olima
Atmosphere	Mlengalenga M'mwamba	Mlengalenga
Available Water Capacity	Madzi Chinyezi	Gawo la madzi mnthaka limene lingathe kugwiritsidwa ndi chomera kudzera mmizu.
Backflow	Kuukha	Madzi akubwerera m'mbuyo.
Best Practice	Njira za makono Njira yabwino	Kugwiritsa ntchito njira za makono zotsimikizika kuti nzaphindu
Birth Rate	Mlingo Mlingo wa Chiwerengero	Mlingo wa chiwerengero cha ana obadwa 100 pa 1000 aliwonse
Carbon Footprint	Kuyeza Muyezo wa	Kuchuluka kwa mpweya woipa omwe watumizidwa mlengalenga nawononga chilengedwe kwa nthawi yonse yomwe: Machiniwo akhala akugwiritsidwa ntchito. Kapena chipangireni chinthu china chake.

<i>Carbon Neutral</i>		
<i>Carbon Taxes</i>		
<i>Carnivores</i>	<i>Nyama</i>	<i>Nyama zomwe zimadya nyama zimnzake</i>
<i>Catchment area</i>	<i>Malo</i>	<i>Malo otetezedwa kumene mitsinje ndi madamu kapenanso madzi a mmapaipi amachokera.</i>
<i>Cell</i>		<i>Tinthu ting'onoting'ono tamoyo timene timapanga thupi la chamoyo. Tinthuti sitimaoneka ndi maso koma ndi makina wotchedwa 'microscope'.</i>
<i>Climate Change</i>	<i>kusintha kwa nyengo</i>	<i>Kusintha kwa nyengo.</i>
<i>Cloud</i>	<i>Mtambo</i>	<i>Zinthu zowoneka ngati utsi zomwe zimayala, namakankhidwa ndi mphepo mlengalenga</i>
<i>Cold Air</i>	<i>Pempho yozizira Kapmphepo kayaziyazi.</i>	<i>Mphepo yozizira.</i>
<i>Commercial and Industrial Waste</i>	<i>Kusamala zinyalala. Zotsalira</i>	<i>Kusamala zinyalala ndi zinyansi zochokera ku makampani, boma ndi nthambi zake komanso ku ma sukulu ndi ma koleji.</i>
<i>Compost</i>	<i>Manyowa Zinthu zowolera mnthaka</i>	<i>Zinthu zomwe zawola mdothi ndipo zasantuka nthaka ya chonde, chakudya cha zomera zina.</i>
<i>Composting</i>	<i>Kuwola Kusanduka manyowa</i>	<i>Kufa ndikuola kwa chinthu. mothandizidwa ndi oxygen</i>

<i>Condensation</i>		
<i>Consumer</i>	<i>Munthu Nyama Makampani</i>	<i>Munthu kapena chinyama, komanso kampani: Amene amagwiritsa ntchito zinthu zina kuti moyo upitilire kapenanso popanga china chake.</i>
<i>Consumption</i>	<i>Kudya Kugwiritsa ntchito</i>	<i>Kuchidya chinthu kapena, kuchigwiritsa ntchito.</i>
<i>Controlled Burning</i>	<i>Kuwotcha zinyalala</i>	<i>Malamulo okhudzana matayidwe a zinyalala.</i>
<i>Crop Rotation</i>	<i>Ulimi wa kasinthasintha</i>	<i>Ulimi wa kasinthasintha</i>
<i>Cyclone</i>	<i>Mphepo</i>	<i>Mphepo yomwe imabweretsa mvula ya mabingu.</i>
<i>Decomposers (e.g., bacteria decomposing matter)</i>	<i>Tizilombo ta matenda</i>	<i>Tizilombo towoletsa zinthu.</i>
<i>Deforestation</i>	<i>Kuwononga Chilengedwe</i>	<i>Kudula mitengo mwachisawawa</i>
<i>Desalinisation</i>	<i>Kuchotsa mchele</i>	<i>Kuchotsa mchele mdothi</i>
<i>Desert</i>	<i>Chipalamba Malo a mchenga okhaokha</i>	<i>Malo opanda zomera ndi nyama kapena ziliko zochepa, malo a mchenga okhaokha.</i>
<i>Dew</i>	<i>Mame</i>	<i>Mame</i>
<i>Drainage</i>	<i>Madzi osapindulitsa.</i>	<i>Ulimi wamthilira kapena wodalira mvula omwe uli osapindulitsa chifukwa choti madzi ambiri amathera kulowa pansu kwambiri ndipo zomera zipindula chifukwa zimalephera kugwiritsa ntchito madziwo.</i>

<i>Drinking Water (potable water)</i>	<i>Madzi akumwa Madzi opanda matenda</i>	<i>Madzi akumwa aukhondo</i>
<i>Drought</i>	<i>Chilala</i>	<i>Kusowa kwa mvula</i>
<i>Dryland Salinity</i>	<i>Mchere wa mnthaka</i>	<i>Kuchuluka kwa mchere mdothi, komanso mmadzi a pansi pa nthaka mwina chifukwa cha chilengedwe kapenso ochita kuikamo.</i>
<i>Ecology</i>	<i>Maphunziro a pa zamoyo</i>	<i>Maphunzilo a pa zamoyo pofuna kuona mmene zimakhallira moyo, ubale wake wa china ndi chimnzake komanso ubale wake ndi malo amene chimakhala.</i>
<i>Ecosystem</i>	<i>Kukhalira pamodzi modalirana Kudalirana kwa za moyo ndi zopanda moyo.</i>	<i>Zochitika za pakati pa zamoyo(zomera ndi nyama) ndinso zopanda moyo zimene zikukhala pamalo amodzi ndi mmene zimakhallira modalirana.</i>
<i>Endangered Species</i>	<i>Chiwopsezo</i>	<i>Zamoyo zomwe zili pa chiwopsezo</i>
<i>Energy</i>	<i>Mphamvu</i>	<i>Kuthekera kopanga chinachake.</i>
<i>Energy Efficiency</i>	<i>Mphamvu</i>	<i>Mphamvu zodalirika</i>
<i>Environment</i>	<i>Zomwe wayandikana nazo Zomwe zakuzungulira</i>	<i>Zinthu zonse zomwe zazungulira chinthu china chake chamoyo kapena chopanda moyo.</i>
<i>Erosion</i>	<i>Kukokoloka kwa nthaka</i>	<i>Kukokoloka kwa nthaka pamalo pamene palibe zomera. Nthaka imakokoloka ndi madzi othamanga, mphepo kapena madzi owundandana</i>

<i>Evaporation</i>	<i>Nthunzi Kuuluka kwa madzi.</i>	<i>Madzi omwe ali mu mlengalenga odza chifukwa cha kutentha.</i>
<i>Feedback</i>	<i>Zotsatira</i>	<i>Zotsatira, kapena yankho la nkhani inayake.</i>
<i>Fertilizers</i>	<i>Fetezeza Mchere wa mnthaka</i>	<i>Mankhwala othira mnthaka kuti ikhale ndi chonde</i>
<i>fog</i>	<i>Chifunga</i>	<i>Timadontho ta madzi tochuluka tomwe tili mlengalenga.</i>
<i>Food Chain</i>	<i>Kudalirana kwa za moyo</i>	<i>Kudalirana kwa za moyo kuti china ndi chakudya cha chimnzake.</i>
<i>Food Security</i>	<i>Kukhala ndi chakudya. Kupezeka kwa chakudya</i>	<i>Kukhala ndi chakudya chokwanira nthawi zonse.Kusakhala ndi njala mdziko.</i>
<i>Forest</i>	<i>Nkhalango Dondo</i>	<i>Malo otetezedwa omwe ali ndi mitengo ndi zomera zina.</i>
<i>Fossil Fuel</i>		
<i>Garden Organics</i>	<i>Zinthu zomera mmakomo</i>	<i>zinthu zomera mmakomo monga maheji, maluwa ndi kapinga</i>
<i>Genome</i>		
<i>Global Warming</i>	<i>Kusintha kwa nyengo. Kutentha kwa dziko lonse</i>	<i>Kutentha kwa dziko lonse la pansi potsatira kusintha kwa nyengo chifukwa cha kuwonongedwa kwa za chilengedwe.</i>
<i>Governance</i>	<i>Utsogoleri</i>	<i>Utsogoleri</i>
<i>Greenhouse effect</i>		<i>Zoipa zomwe zadza ndi ulimi wamakono.</i>
<i>Greenhouse Gas</i>	<i>Mpweya</i>	<i>Mpweya ochokera ku ulimi wamakono.</i>
<i>Groundwater</i>	<i>Madzi a nthaka</i>	<i>Madzi opezeka mtimipata ta dothi</i>

		<i>komanso mming'alu ya miyala ya pansu pa nthaka.</i>
<i>Growth</i>	<i>Kukula</i>	<i>Kusintha kwa chinthu mu zaka, nsinkhu ndi thupi.</i>
<i>Habitat</i>	<i>Malo</i>	<i>Kumalo kumene chinthu chimakhalako pamoyo wake</i>
<i>Heat</i>	<i>Kutentha</i>	<i>Kutentha</i>
<i>Heavy Rain</i>	<i>Mvula yambiri Mvula yosakata</i>	<i>Mvula yochuluka.</i>
<i>Herbicide</i>	<i>Mankhwala</i>	<i>Mankhwala ophera zomera kapenena kusokonezera moyo wa zomera.</i>
<i>Herbivores</i>	<i>Nyama zodya thengo</i>	<i>Nyama zomwe zimadalira zomera ngati chakudya chake pa moyo wake onse.</i>
<i>High pressure area</i>	<i>Malo osowa chakudya Malo otentha</i>	<i>Kumalo kumene za moyo zikukanganirana chakudya chifukwa cha kusowa kwa chakudya. Malo otentha, malo odikha, otsika okhala kufupi ndi nyanja.</i>
<i>Hydrosphere</i>	<i>Madzi</i>	<i>Gawo la dziko lapansi lomwe latengedwa ndi madzi mnjira zosiyanasiyana monga nyanja yamchere, khwawa, mitsinje, nyanja.mmadamu, mdothi kapenanso mu mlengalenga.</i>
<i>Incineration</i>	<i>Kuotcha zinyalala. Kuwocha zinyansi.</i>	<i>Kuotcha moto zinthu zomwe zagwiritsidwa ntchito ngati njira yosamalira chilengedwe.</i>
<i>Industrial Agriculture</i>	<i>Makampani pa za ulimi</i>	<i>Makampani amene amapanga mankhwala komanso zipangizo za</i>

		<i>ulimi.</i>
<i>Infiltration</i>	<i>Madzi akulowa pansu Kulowa pansu kwa madzi</i>	<i>Kulowa pansu kwa madzi kuti mizu iwagwiritse ntchito.</i>
<i>Inorganic Matter</i>		
<i>Intercropping</i>	<i>Ulimi wa kasakaniza</i>	<i>Ulimi womadzala mbewu zamitundu ingapo pamzere umodzi mnyenngo yodzala yofanana</i>
<i>Irrigation</i>	<i>Ulimi wamthirira Ulimi wa chilimwe</i>	<i>Ulimi wosadalira madzi amvula. Ulimi womathirira mbewu. Ulimi wa nthawi ya chilimwe.</i>
<i>Land Use</i>	<i>Ubwino wa malo</i>	<i>Kagwiritsidwe ntchito ka malo.</i>
<i>Landfill</i>	<i>Zinyalala zomwe zakwiliridwa</i>	<i>Kukwilira zinyalala mdothi zoti zili ndi kuthekera koti zitha kuola nkusanduka dothi.</i>
<i>Landfill gas</i>	<i>Mpweya woipa</i>	<i>Mpweya woipa wochokera ku zinyalala zomwe zingathe kuola zitakwiliridwa mdothi.</i>
<i>Lightning</i>		
<i>Low pressure area</i>		
<i>Microorganism</i>	<i>Kanthu kamoyo</i>	<i>Kanthu kamoyo koma kosaoneka ndi maso anthu koma ndi makina a 'microscope' chomera kapena kachilombo.</i>
<i>Mist</i>		<i>Chinthu chosaoneka bwinobwino ndipo kuti nchovuta kuchifotokoza maonekedwe ake.</i>
<i>Monoculture</i>	<i>Ulimi</i>	<i>Ulimi womalima mbewu imodzi</i>

		<i>pamundapo panyengo imeneyo.</i>
<i>Mortality Rate</i>	<i>Imfa</i>	<i>Imfa ya zamoyo 100 pa 1000 zilizonse.</i>
<i>Natural</i>	<i>Chilengedwe</i>	<i>Kupezeka kwa zachilengedwe monga mpweya, madzi,malo/nthaka/dothi komanso dzuwa.</i>
<i>Natural resources</i>	<i>Zinthu zachilengedwe</i>	<i>Zinthu zonse zimene zili zachilengedwe</i>
<i>Noise pollution</i>	<i>Phokoso</i>	<i>Phokoso lowononga makutu, lolepheretsa kumvana polankhulana komanso losokoneza kugona tulo.</i>
<i>Nutrients</i>	<i>Chakudya</i>	<i>.Zakudya zofunikira mthupi la munthu kapena nyama. .Chakudya chofunikira cha chomera kuchokera mnthaka yabwino.</i>
<i>Pesticide</i>	<i>Mankhwala</i>	<i>Mankhwala ophera tizilombo towononga.</i>
<i>Plastic</i>	<i>Pulasitiki</i>	<i>Ziwiya ndi zipangizo/zida zonse za pulasitiki.</i>
<i>Pollution</i>	<i>Kuwononga</i>	<i>Kuonongeka kwa zinthu izi: Phokoso: Mpweya:mpweya oipa ochokera ku makina a makono. Madzi:mankhwala omwe aikidwa m'madzimo Nthaka:mankhwala monga fetereza wothilidwa mthaka.</i>
<i>Power</i>	<i>Mphamvu</i>	<i>Mphamvu yopangitsa kuti china chake chichitike</i>
<i>Precipitation</i>	<i>Mvula</i>	<i>Mtundu uliwonse wamadzi amene akugwa kuchokera mu mlengalenga</i>

<i>Precipitation</i>		
<i>Producer</i>		<i>Mkulu wopanga ma programme pa wailesi. Chomera chomwe chili tsinde la chakudya cha nyama zingapo mu ndondomeko ya kudalirana kwa zamoyo.</i>
<i>Product</i>	<i>Chinthu</i>	<i>Chinthu chomwe chapangidwa kuchokera ku 'Industry'. Chinthu chomwe chikugulitsidwa.</i>
<i>Productivity</i>	<i>Phindu</i>	<i>Phindu lomwe ladza kuchokera pa ntchito yomwe yachitika.</i>
<i>Rain</i>	<i>Mvula</i>	<i>Madzi amene akugwa kuchokera mlengalenga</i>
<i>Rainwater</i>	<i>Madzi a mvula</i>	<i>Madzi amvula amene agwa kale panthaka kapena asungidwa mnjira zina.</i>
<i>Rainwater harvesting</i>	<i>Kukolola madzi a mvula Madzi amkolola</i>	<i>Kupanga madamu kapena mathanki osungira madzi okhawa amvula kuti adzagwiritsidwe ntchito mtsogolo.</i>
<i>Raw materials</i>		<i>Zinthu za chilengedwe zomwe sizinapititsidwe ku 'Industry' komwe zikasinthidwe mmaonekedwe ndi ka gwiritsidwe ntchito.</i>
<i>Recycling</i>	<i>Chibwereza</i>	<i>Chinthu chomwe mwachigwiritsa ntchito,kuchikonzanso kuti muchigwiritsenso ntchito mwina m'ntchito yomweyo kapenanso mnjira ina.</i>
<i>Reforestation</i>	<i>Kubwezeretsa chilengedwe</i>	<i>Kudzalanso mitengo mobwezeretsa yomwe</i>

	<i>Kudzalanso mitengo.</i>	<i>mwadula.</i>
<i>Reuse</i>	<i>Chibwereza Kugwiritsanso ntchito</i>	<i>Kugwiritsa ntchito chinthu mobwerezabwereza.</i>
<i>Risk</i>	<i>Vuto</i>	<i>Vuto</i>
<i>Septic sewage</i>	<i>Suweji</i>	<i>Malo otayira nyansi za nzimbuzi ndipo utha kukazitenga nyansizo ndikungira manyowa.</i>
<i>Sewage</i>	<i>Suweji</i>	<i>Kumene mapayipi a nzimbuzi za madzi amakathera.</i>
<i>Soil</i>	<i>Dothi</i>	<i>Dothi.</i>
<i>Sun</i>	<i>Dzuwa</i>	<i>Dzuwa</i>
<i>System</i>	<i>Chilinganizo</i>	<i>Njira ya mmene zinthu zimayendera</i>
<i>Topsoil</i>	<i>Dothi lapamwamba</i>	<i>Dothi lapamwamba pa nthaka.</i>
<i>Tropical Cyclone</i>	<i>Mphepo</i>	<i>Mphepo yochokera kummawa ndiku madzulo yomwe imabweretsa mvula mmaiko opezeka pakati pa dziko la pansi.</i>
<i>Warm Air</i>	<i>Mpweya wotenterako</i>	<i>Kamphepo kotenterako pang'ono</i>
<i>Waste</i>	<i>zinyalala</i>	<i>Zinyalala</i>
<i>Waste Management</i>	<i>Masamalidwe a zinyalala</i>	<i>Masamalidwe a zinyalala</i>
<i>Water Cycle</i>	<i>Zokhudza madzi</i>	<i>Madzi amachokera kuti? Za mmene madzi amapezekerera pa dziko lapansi.</i>
<i>Water Quality</i>	<i>Madzi abwino</i>	<i>Zizindikiro za madzi a ukhondo, madzi a bwino.</i>
<i>Water Table</i>	<i>Madzi a pansi panthaka</i>	<i>Madzi omwe akuchokera pansi</i>

		<i>panthaka pachifukwa choti nthakayo ili ndi madzi ambiri.</i>
<i>Weather</i>	<i>Nyengo</i>	<i>Nyengo yatsiku ndi tsiku.</i>
<i>Wetlands</i>	<i>Malo a chinyontho</i>	<i>Madera omwe mvula siikata, imagwa kawirikawiri.</i>
<i>Wind Energy</i>	<i>Makina oyendera mphepo</i>	<i>Kugwiritsa ntchito mphepo poyendetsa makina</i>
<i>Wind Turbine</i>	<i>Mphepo</i>	<i>Kusinthasintha kwa mbali yochokera mphepo</i>
<i>Work</i>	<i>Ntchito</i>	<i>Ntchito</i>